

PARAMETRIC STUDY ON BENDING RESPONSE OF RECTANGULAR CFST BEAMS

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Abstract

This paper presents a parametric study on the influence of steel quantity, varied through different tube thicknesses, on the behavior of concrete-filled rectangular steel tubular (CFST) beams subjected to pure bending. A fiber-element-based numerical analysis approach is employed to develop a computational program, implemented using Oracle-10g Forms 6i, to perform the parametric investigations. The beam specimens have a span of 1000 mm, with a constant width of 120 mm and varying depths from 160 mm to 260 mm. The steel tubes are filled with concrete having compressive strengths ranging from 48 MPa to 64 MPa. The primary variables in this study are the increment in steel area and the concrete compressive strength. Their effects on the flexural capacity and overall structural response of CFST beams are numerically evaluated, presented, and discussed.

Keywords: Fiber element analysis, CFST, flexural capacity, ductility, bending

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite steel-concrete construction is widely used in building and bridge engineering, including regions of high seismic risk. This form of construction effectively combines the advantages of both materials, offering high load-carrying capacity, stiffness, rapid construction, and overall economy [1]. Tomii and Sakino [2] conducted tests on eight CFT beam-column specimens with width-to-thickness ratios ranging from 23.5 to 45 to investigate their strength behavior. Prion and Boehme [3] tested four CFT beams with a diameter-to-thickness ratio of 89.4, filled with concrete of cylinder strength 73 MPa, and reported that all specimens exhibited highly ductile failure.

Experimental investigations have traditionally been the primary method of studying CFST behavior; however, numerical modeling is becoming increasingly important due to its ability to simulate cases that are difficult to reproduce experimentally [4]. Several researchers have proposed analytical approaches for estimating the flexural capacity of CFST beams [2], [5], [6]. Gupta and Katariya developed a fiber-element analysis model within an Oracle database environment [7] and examined the flexural capacity of CFST beams under pure bending. Their study evaluated the influence of cross-sectional shape, concrete grade, and steel tube strength, and compared the moment capacities of rectangular and square sections with equal cross-sectional area. They concluded that the moment capacity of rectangular sections increases at a diminishing rate with higher steel grades compared with square sections when high-strength steel tubes are used [8]. In another study, they investigated square sections with varying cross-sectional areas and found that flexural capacity increases progressively with increasing sectional area [9].

The existing literature shows that the influence of varying D/B , D/t , and B/t ratios on the moment capacity of rectangular concrete-filled steel tubular beams remains largely unexplored, where D is the depth, B is the width of the composite section, and t is the steel tube thickness. In the present study, virtual rectangular beams are designed by keeping B constant while increasing D and t to obtain different D/B , D/t , and B/t ratios, with the concrete and steel grades kept unchanged. A parametric investigation is then carried out using a fiber-element analysis code developed in the Oracle database to examine the effects of steel tube cross-sectional area on the flexural capacity of rectangular CFST beams.

2. PARAMETRIC STUDY

2.1 Computer code and its verification

The computer code based on the fiber element analysis method was developed using Oracle-10g Forms 6i. The efficiency and accuracy of this code have been previously demonstrated through comparisons with experimental results reported by the authors in an earlier study [7]. In the fiber element approach, the composite beam section is discretized into a number of small elements, referred to as fibers. For a given input curvature, the strain distribution across the depth of the section is computed. Using the appropriate stress–strain relationships for steel and concrete, the stress in each fiber corresponding to its strain value is determined.

The force in each fiber is then obtained by multiplying the stress by the fiber area. The neutral axis depth is evaluated through an iterative procedure to satisfy equilibrium conditions. Once the neutral axis and fiber stresses are known, the bending moment corresponding to any specified curvature can be calculated. In experimental testing, curvature is induced directly by the external load applied to the beam specimen, whereas in the numerical model it is used as a controlling input parameter.

2.2.1 Stress-Strain Behaviour of Steel and Concrete

The stress–strain relationships for steel and concrete were incorporated into the computer code. The adopted stress–strain curves for structural steel and confined concrete are shown in Fig. 1. For mild steel, the strain values corresponding to the onset of strain hardening (ϵ_{st}) and the ultimate strain (ϵ_{su}) are taken as 0.005 and 0.20, respectively, following the idealized curve O–A–B–C. The yield strain (ϵ_{sy}) is computed using the modulus of elasticity of steel (E_s) and the yield strength (f_{sy}), as recommended in [6]. Modulus of elasticity of concrete (E_c) is calculated by ACI [10].

$$E_c = 3320 \sqrt{f'_{cc}} + 6900 \text{ MPa} \quad (1)$$

Where f'_{cc} is compressive cylinder strength of concrete in MPa.

Fig. 1 Stress-strain relationship for (i) steel and (ii) concrete in concrete-filled steel tube

The stress–strain curve for confined concrete is idealized into four segments in compression (O–A, A–B, B–C, and C–D) and two segments in tension (O–S and S–Q). The concrete stress in the initial ascending branch from O to A is evaluated using the equation proposed by Mander et al. [11].

$$\sigma_c = \frac{f'_{cc} \lambda (\epsilon_{cc} / \epsilon'_{cc})}{\lambda - 1 + (\epsilon_{cc} / \epsilon'_{cc})^\lambda} \quad (2)$$

Where,

σ_c =longitudinal compressive stress in concrete at any part of compression

ϵ_{cc} =longitudinal compressive strain in concrete at any part of compression

f'_{cc} =compressive cylinder strength of concrete in MPa

ϵ'_{cc} =strain in concrete corresponding to stress f'_{cc}

λ is a parameter = $E_c / (E_c - (f'_{cc} / \epsilon'_{cc}))$

ϵ_{to} =tensile strain in concrete at cracking

ϵ_{tu} = ultimate tensile strain in concrete

The stress in the confined concrete stress-strain curve part AB, BC and CD is calculated as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_c &= f'_{cc} && \text{for } \epsilon'_{cc} < \epsilon_{cc} \leq 0.005 \\ \sigma_c &= \beta_c f'_{cc} + 100 (0.015 - \epsilon_{cc}) (f'_{cc} - \beta_c f'_{cc}) && \text{for } 0.005 < \epsilon_{cc} \leq 0.015 \\ \sigma_c &= \beta_c f'_{cc} && \text{for } \epsilon_{cc} > 0.015 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The value of β_c depends upon the β_s/t ratio, as proposed by Liang [12] .

$$\beta_c = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{if } \beta_s/t < 24 \\ 1.5 - (\beta_s/48t) & \text{if } 24 < \beta_s/t \leq 48 \\ 0.5 & \text{if } \beta_s/t > 48 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Where, t is the wall thickness of steel section. β_s is taken as the larger of width and depth for a rectangular section.

For concrete in tension zone, tensile strength of concrete (f_{ct}) corresponding to strain ϵ_{to} . ϵ_{to} is taken as $0.6\sqrt{f'_{cc}}$. The concrete tensile stress is proportional to tensile strain of concrete upto its cracking. After cracking, the strain in concrete is inversely proportional to stress in concrete. The ultimate strain is taken as 10 times of the strain at cracking ($\epsilon_{tu} = 10 \epsilon_{to}$) [6].

3 BEAM SPECIMENS

The span of all beam specimens is taken as 1000 mm. A typical sectional view is shown in Fig. 2. The steel tubes have a yield strength of 260 MPa, an ultimate tensile strength of 320 MPa, and a modulus of elasticity of 205 GPa. The tubes are filled with concrete having compressive strengths ranging from 48 MPa to 64 MPa. The detailed dimensions of all beam sections are provided in Table 1.

Fig. 2 Typical view of composite section

4 RESULTS

The following paragraphs present the key findings of the parametric study. The results are discussed in terms of different structural aspects of the beam section.

4.1 Influence of Increment in Steel Area

The steel content in the specimens was varied as 5.51%, 10%, 15%, and 20% of the total composite cross-sectional area. To maintain a constant composite area, the steel tube thickness was increased uniformly on all four sides. The results indicate that the moment capacity of CFST beams increases proportionally with the increase in steel area.

As shown in Table 1, the moment ratio ranges from **1.60 to 1.61** when the steel area increases from 5.51% to 10%; from **2.17 to 2.25** when increased from 5.51% to 15%; and from **2.75 to 2.81** when the steel area increases from 5.51% to 20%. Figures 3 to 8 illustrate the progressive rise in moment capacity under pure bending corresponding to the increment in steel tube area.

These results clearly demonstrate that increasing the steel tube area independently enhances the flexural capacity of rectangular CFST beams in pure bending, irrespective of the overall sectional size.

Table 1 Details of simulated CFST beams

B (mm)	D (mm)	t (mm)	A_s/A_g (%)	f'_{cc} (MPa)	Moment (kN-m)	Moment Ratio
120	160	1.81	05.51	48.80	19.81	1.00
120	160	3.19	10.00	48.80	31.84	1.61
120	160	4.62	15.00	48.80	44.60	2.25
120	160	5.97	20.00	48.80	55.55	2.80
120	190	1.94	05.51	52.00	27.64	1.00
120	190	3.42	10.00	52.00	44.40	1.61
120	190	4.95	15.00	52.00	62.00	2.24
120	190	6.39	20.00	52.00	77.70	2.81
120	250	2.14	05.51	48.00	46.65	1.00
120	250	3.76	10.00	48.00	74.64	1.60
120	250	5.44	15.00	48.00	102.04	2.19
120	250	7.02	20.00	48.00	129.40	2.77

120	170	1.86	05.51	64.18	22.87	1.00
120	170	3.27	10.00	64.18	36.82	1.61
120	170	4.74	15.00	64.18	51.34	2.25
120	170	6.12	20.00	64.18	64.02	2.80
120	200	1.98	05.51	62.88	31.34	1.00
120	200	3.48	10.00	62.88	50.10	1.60
120	200	5.05	15.00	62.88	69.24	2.22
120	200	6.51	20.00	62.88	87.23	2.78
120	260	2.17	05.51	60.00	51.80	1.00
120	260	3.81	10.00	60.00	82.77	1.60
120	260	5.51	15.00	60.00	112.32	2.17
120	260	7.11	20.00	60.00	142.72	2.75

Where A_s and A_g are the sectional area of steel tube and area of composite section respectively.

Fig. 3 Comparison of moments vs deflection for section having depth 160 mm

Fig.4 Comparison of moments vs deflection for section having depth 190 mm

Fig. 5 Comparison of moments vs deflection for section having depth 250 mm

Fig. 6 Comparison of moments vs deflection for section having depth 170 mm

Fig. 7 Comparison of moments vs deflection for section having depth 200 mm

Fig. 8 Comparison of moments vs deflection for section having depth 260 mm

Fig. 9 Comparison of variation of neutral axis depth vs deflection for section having depth 160 mm

Fig. 10 Comparison of variation of neutral axis depth vs deflection for section having depth 190 mm

Fig. 11 Comparison of variation of neutral axis depth vs deflection for section having depth 250 mm

Fig. 12 Comparison of variation of neutral axis depth vs deflection for section having depth 170 mm

Fig. 13 Comparison of variation of neutral axis depth vs deflection for section having depth 200 mm

Fig. 14 Comparison of variation of neutral axis depth vs deflection for section having depth 260 mm

4.2 Influence of Neutral Axis Depth

The neutral axis depth is measured from the extreme compression fiber. The curves plotted between neutral axis depth and central deflection (Fig. 9 to Fig. 14) indicate that the neutral axis gradually shifts downward as the steel tube area increases for a given section. This downward movement reflects the increasing contribution of concrete in resisting curvature.

Sections with lower concrete area exhibit a slower shift in the neutral axis compared to sections with larger concrete areas. For specimens with 20% steel content, the neutral axis depth stabilizes relatively early during bending. In contrast, for specimens with 5.51% steel content, the neutral axis moves slowly and does not fully stabilize within the analyzed curvature range.

4.3 Influence of Concrete Compressive Strength

As curvature increases, the neutral axis progressively moves toward the compression side of the composite section. The curves relating neutral axis depth to deflection show that the concrete area in the compression zone contributes effectively to resisting external loads. However, the results indicate that the concrete compressive strength has only a marginal influence on enhancing the flexural strength, particularly when the steel tube area is increased. The interaction effect between higher concrete strength and increased steel tube thickness does not produce significant additional gains in flexural capacity.

5. Conclusions

A total of twenty-four virtual concrete-filled rectangular steel tube (CFST) beams were simulated to investigate the influence of steel tube sectional area on flexural capacity. A fiber-element analysis code was developed in an Oracle database environment to conduct this parametric study. All beams ultimately failed due to yielding of the tension-side steel.

The study shows that the neutral axis position stabilizes earlier in sections with higher steel content. For sections with uniform steel tube thickness, the steel on the compression side is not fully utilized because the neutral axis remains close to the top fiber, while yielding occurs in the tension steel. Therefore, it may be concluded that the efficiency of steel usage can be improved by reducing the tube thickness on the compression side and reallocating that material to the tension side. This redistribution could enhance the moment capacity of CFST beams without altering the total steel quantity.

6. REFERENCES

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